

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- III April - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

The Psycho-Physiological Impact of Yoga on Stress Management among College Students in the Age of Artificial Intelligence

Paper Id : 20099 Submission Date : 2025-04-06 Acceptance Date : 2025-04-20 Publication Date : 2025-04-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15524379

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Abstract

This study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the psycho-physiological effects of yoga on stress management among college students in the current era of Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI has rapidly integrated into numerous aspects of daily life, from personal assistants on smart phones to the algorithms that drive social media feeds. While AI has the potential to revolutionize the way we live and work, it is not without its drawbacks. "As dependence on these technologies increases, there is growing concern regarding their potential negative impacts on mental health and well-being, particularly among college students. College students are in a critical period of developmental maturation, facing rigorous academic demands while learning to function independently. Physical activities such as running and bicycling have been shown to improve mood and relieve stress. However, college students often exhibit low levels of physical activity, partly due to the growing influence of AI." This research explores the potential psychological impacts of AI usage, including anxiety, addiction, social isolation, and depression, and discusses strategies to mitigate these risks. Yoga, an ancient physical and mental discipline, is known to positively affect mood and stress levels. The objective of this study is to establish preliminary evidence for the psycho-physiological effects of yoga on stress among young adult college students.

Keywords Mental health, Yoga, Stress, Artificial intelligence (AI), Psycho-physiological effects.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has garnered significant attention and inquisition across various fields, including higher education. This study analyze the influence of AI on students and examine its negative impact on graduates' future careers. The results indicate that AI plays a crucial role, in leading to various health complications. The findings emphasize the effectiveness and efficiency of yoga as a stress management system. "Approximately 40%–50% of college students are physically inactive. In the modern world, sedentary lifestyles have become increasingly common due to the growing influence of AI, resulting in prolonged periods of sitting or engaging in low levels of physical activity. This sedentary behaviour can have detrimental effects on both physical and mental health. A sedentary lifestyle can contribute to numerous physical health complications, including obesity, cardiovascular disease, and musculoskeletal problems." Furthermore, sedentary behaviour adversely affects mental well-being, increasing the risk of depression and anxiety, and leading to poor sleep quality. Stress significantly impacts college students' social, mental, physical, and intellectual health. College students often lack the necessary stress management skills and coping strategies. Physical activity is a coping strategy that is underutilized by many college students. Daily participation in physical activity is a primary factor in maintaining sound health in modern society.

Objective of study

1. To investigate the increasing levels of stress among college students due to the influence of Artificial Intelligence (AI).
2. To examine the physiological effects of yoga on college students.
3. To emphasize the psychological benefits of yoga for college students

Review of Literature

Psychological impacts of using AI systems

The most important concerns are the potential loss of human connection. "Traditional classrooms promote deep interpersonal relationships between students and teachers, providing emotional support and personal guidance. In contrast, AI-driven learning experiences may lack the empathetic and compassionate touch that human instructors offer, possibly affecting students' emotional well-being and engagement. The over reliance on technology may hinder students' critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Relying too heavily on AI might reduce students' ability to think creatively and independently. With the increasing prevalence of AI-powered devices, people may become addicted to technology, leading to symptoms such as anxiety, depression, and sleep disorders."⁶

1. **Anxiety:** "Some people may feel anxious when using AI systems because they are not sure how the system works or what outcomes to expect. For example, if someone is using a speech recognition system to transcribe their voice, they may feel anxious if they are unsure if the system is accurately capturing their words."⁷
2. **Addiction:** Overutilization of technology, including AI systems, can lead to habit-forming behaviors. People may feel compelled to constantly check their devices or use AI-powered apps, which can interfere with other aspects of their lives, such as work or social relationships.⁸
3. **Reduced Sense of Community or Social isolation:** "People who spend too much time interacting with AI systems may become socially isolated, as they may spend less time engaging with other people in person. This can lead to decreased sense of community or connection to others."
4. **AI-generated Deepfake videos:** "Deepfakes are videos that use AI to manipulate or replace an individual's image or voice in a video or audio recording. These videos can be used to disperse false information or malicious content, which can have a strong psychological impact on the person depicted in the video."
5. **Virtual assistants:** For instance, Siri or Alexa, can create a sense of dependency and make it harder for individuals to engage in real-life social interactions.

Main Text

Physiological impacts of using AI systems

A sedentary lifestyle can contribute to several physical health complications, including:⁹

1. **Obesity:** "Lack of physical action and excessive sitting can lead to weight gain and obesity. When energy intake surpasses energy expenditure, it can result in an

- disequilibrium that promotes weight gain.”
2. **Cardiovascular Disease:** “Prolonged sitting and inactivity are associated with an increased risk of developing cardiovascular diseases such as heart disease, high blood pressure, and high cholesterol levels.”
 3. **Type 2 Diabetes:** “Sedentary behavior is a significant risk factor for developing type 2 diabetes. Lack of physical activity impairs insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism, leading to insulin resistance.”
 4. **Musculoskeletal Problems:** “Sitting for long periods can lead to muscle imbalances, weakened bones, and poor posture. It may contribute to back pain, neck pain, and musculoskeletal disorders.”

In modern time and fast-paced world, everyone is realizing the need for peaceful breaks in between their continuous hectic lives. Yoga is an ancient Indian science and way of life that brings about relaxation and also induces a balanced mental state. In yoga the mind reaches a neutral stage thereby relieving mental exhaustion.¹⁰ “Mental health treatment is the need of the hour. Yoga is a physical, mental, and spiritual practice. It includes the practice of ‘Niyama’ (social ethics), ‘yama’ (personal ethics), ‘[pranayama](#)’ (breathing exercises), [asana](#) (physical postures) and ‘[meditation](#)’ (science of relaxing the mind). These can improve student mental health by teaching students to balance success and failure.”

Yoga

The involvement in physical activity on a daily basis is one of the primary factors in maintaining good health in modern society. “Due to sedentary lifestyles leading to many health-related issues, the prevalence of physical inactivity among college students calls for immediate action.¹¹ Along with aerobics and dance, yoga is one of the most famous physical activities that college girls would like to prefer as choice.”¹² “Physical activities, such as yoga, is a key element in health promotion. Yoga is one of India’s greatest endowment to the world. Yoga deals with the body, mind and behavior in a synergistic way. Yoga refers to the union between body and mind. The practice of yoga makes an individual think and lives in a proper way with a philosophical view. It improves the quality of life and brings health and harmony to society. The holistic science of yoga is the best method for prevention as well as management of stress and stress induced disorders.¹³ The effectiveness of yoga for stress management is well established.”¹⁴ In today’s education system, a student becomes a victim of stress, which in turn affects the mood, behavior, cognition and academic performance of the student and in turn, their physical health too.¹⁵ Yoga is most useful in controlling and treating stress in the present day scenario.¹⁶

“The traditional expressions of yoga as a lifestyle is firmly rooted in and committed to the classic texts (e.g., the yoga Sutra by Patanjali, Hatha Yoga) and embrace the concept of the eight limbs, or aspects, of yoga. In more specific term, the eight limbs are of great interest to yogis who seek to adhere to yoga as a philosophical foundation for life rather than solely a physical practice.¹⁷ Therefore, yoga is essentially an art and science of holistic living- an effective method for improving health in addition to the prevention and management of diseases.¹⁸ Yoga reduces stress through reducing sympathetic activity, and improves the sense of general well-being.”¹⁹

Stress and college students

“Stress is an emotional and physical response you experience. It may be defined as any situation that tends to disturb the equilibrium between a living organism and its environment. In day-to-day life, there are many stressful situations.” A college student can be stressful due to many causes during study, like academic pressure, family expectations, personal expectations, time management, financial constraints, examinations, competitions, struggling to reach educational goals, job outlook, etc.²⁰ Exams or academic load are the main sources of perceived stress among adolescent students. When you’re constantly stressed for a long time, it is harmful as it may affect your mental and physical health. “Chronic stress can cause long-term or permanent alterations in mental, physiological, and behavioral responses.²¹ Stress affects college

students' physical, mental, social, and intellectual health. A college student will not always possess the necessary stress management skills and coping strategies. Physical activity is one coping strategy that is applied by many college students."

Physiological effects of yoga on college students

"Yoga holds potential as a self-empowering method for enhancing stress management and wellness in college students.²² Yoga includes specific body postures (asanas), breathing techniques (Pranayamas), and meditation to attain the highest level of consciousness. Yogic asana and pranayamas have been shown to reduce the resting respiratory rate, increase the vital capacity, maximum voluntary ventilation, breath-holding time, maximal aspiratory and expiratory pressure; lower blood pressure, improve heart rate, promote healthy circulation, and improve muscle tone."²³ "Yogic Asanas, often thought of as a form of physical exercise are really powerful techniques that play an important role in keeping the body in a balanced position, cultivating awareness, relaxation, concentration, and meditation. Asana is complementary to exercise because in this process there is the development of good physical health through stretching and massaging to affect body mechanisms."

"Yoga also influences overall well-being, quality of life, autonomic function, and immunity. The energy in the body is prana. By controlling the motion of the lungs or respiratory organs, one can control the prana. Through the control of prana, the mind can be easily controlled.²⁴ Stretching, deep breathing and meditation can improve overall physical fitness, strength, flexibility, and lung capacity. Yoga practice results in significant improvements in resting pulse rate, vital capacity, and blood pressure among middle-aged men. Regular practice of yoga improves physical variables (muscular strength, endurance of the trunk, and flexibility) and physiological variables (pulse rate, vital capacity, and peak flow rate) significantly.²⁵ A Yoga-based lifestyle makes a significant change in the social adjustment and behaviour of the students.²⁶ Yoga can improve sattva guna (balance personality trait) among students, thus paving the way for their academic excellence."²⁷

Psychological effects of yoga on college students

From body position to yogic breathing, yoga authorize a student with the ability to remain calm and clear in both unfavorable and favorable conditions. "Practicing yoga lets the body's owner get complete control in terms of response, whether it is physical, psychological, or emotional. Yoga also does a great deal to reduce the symptoms of mental disorders. It assist students develop consciousness of their thought process, enabling them to perceive the external as well as the internal world. This makes students worse able to handle any triggers that usually call up mental illness and/or negative emotions. Suryanamaskara, a yogic practice is effective in leading to relaxation dispositions such as physical relaxation, mental quiet, at ease/peace, being rested and refreshed, strength, awareness, joy and reducing sleepiness, somatic stress, worry and negative emotion at a dispositional level."²⁸ "Yogic practices play an important role in enhancing emotional sensitivity,²⁹ sustained attention,³⁰ mental performance,³¹ and balance personality traits³² among students, thus paving the way for their academic excellence."

1. **Promote Mindfulness** : "Mindfulness is observing the thought patterns of your mind without any judgment or inquiry. Yoga and mindfulness are two sides of the same coin, as both aim to relaxing the mind. So, it can be said that, while practicing yoga with a certain level of awareness, you're practicing mindfulness. Different meditation techniques practiced in yoga involve mindfulness. For example, pranayama breathing techniques help yoga participants attain a state of mindfulness by focus on particular ways of breathing."
2. **Build Self-Confidence** : "All yoga practices and philosophy bring your scattered awareness from the external world to the inside. In this way, yoga makes you more aware of your existence and teaches you that you're completely yourself. This sense of incorporation increases the self-confidence of students, which may prevent many mental health issues. Yoga poses such as Tree Pose, Bridge Pose,

Plank Pose, and Warrior Pose not only tone up us physically but mentally also. These empowering poses can help build self-confidence.”

3. **Reduce Stress** : “Stress due to various reasons, including anger, grief, guilt, and low self-esteem, is very common among college students. This stress may lead to many physical and psychological effects, including headaches, muscle aches, nausea, insomnia, and difficulty concentrating. Yoga effectively works by uniting the body and mind as one unit. It improves many physical and mental ailments that cause stress at a harmful level.”
4. **Helps Concentration**: “Lack of concentration and mental illness are nearly related to each other. Symptoms of mental disorders damage numerous parts of the brain that affect our ability to concentrate on work. Yoga, especially meditation techniques, helps the brain recover its ability to concentrate. Furthermore, the improved concentration can also block anxiety and depression from incoming the mind.”
5. **Improves Social Development** : “Yoga is a great social-emotional learning tool for students. In fact, parents in the United States are encouraging their children to practice yoga in school for their social development. Fast social change is one of the associated causes of poor mental health. Feeling lonely at college, for example, can lead to symptoms of depression.³³ A study conducted by a yoga school in India shows the effect of yogic practices on the social adjustment of college students in urban areas. Using “social adjustment inventory,”³⁴ the social behavior of student groups (those practicing yoga and the non-practicing students) was measured. The study pretending that the yoga group students had improved social behavior and easy adjusted to rapid social changes.”
6. **Bottom Line** : “Yoga as a mental health practice is a tool for college students to handle different obstacles in their academics and to support them psychologically. Yoga considers physical activity, breath work, and mind-calming practices that work to settle over stimulated minds.” To assess the psycho-physiological effects of yoga on stress in college students, some simple yoga practices can be used to reduce stress.³⁵ “These include: starting prayer, Kapalbhathi Kriya (frontal brain cleansing), Agnisar Kriya (activating the digestive fire), hands in and out breathing, hands stretching breathing, ankle stretching breathing, jogging, forward and backward bending, side bending, twisting, Surya namaskara (salutations to the sun practice), Tadasan (palm tree pose), Vrikshasana (tree pose), Padahastasan (hand to foot pose), Ardha Chakrasana (half wheel pose), Bhujangasana (cobra pose) and Shalabhasana (locust pose).”
7. **Quick Relaxation Technique** : “Nadi Shuddhi Pranayama (psychic network purification), Sheetal Pranayama (cooling breath), Seetkari Pranayama (hissing breath), Bhramari Pranayama (humming bee breath), Om Meditation, Closing Prayer.”

Methodology

In this research work both historical and analytical methods were used. The secondary sources were used like books, articles, research papers, research journals, magazines, and newspapers.

Conclusion

The present review study suggests that yoga has positive effects on the psycho-physiological level that lead to increased academic performance in college student. Further research on the relationship between yoga practice and college students is warranted to confirm the efficacy of yoga and to include it in the syllabus of the college student.

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